

“An Empirical Study on Customer Preference and Loyalty on Automobile Brands (cars) among IT Professionals in Bangalore”.

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Abstract

The automobile industry today is the most profit making industry in India. It is one of the largest in the world which contributes to the global sales of automobiles which is set to grow. It plays a significant role in the economic development around the world. Consumer attitude towards the purchase of product varies due to the dynamic change in the standard of living, change in technology and trend. Therefore knowing and analysing these factors is important. Knowing consumer behaviour is vital, as it acts as a successful tool for marketers to achieve their sales objective. Study of consumer behaviour is still a researchable area, with respect to brand loyalty in particular. Brand loyalty has become an important strategy and has greatly contributed to the brand success. This study empirically attempts to investigate the relationship between some of the major dimensions of brand loyalty among the IT professionals in Bangalore. The main aim of the study is to discuss and analyse the brand loyalty of consumers towards the car brands. This research work provides an insight of the brand preference of the customers and the reasons for shifting from one brand over the other. Therefore an online survey through questionnaire survey of 120 respondents was conducted in Bangalore city. From the data collected through questionnaires, the findings which can be reflected is that the majority of the customers are ready to buy the same brand even if the brand price is increased in comparison to its competitor's brand. Hence it is evident that customers are loyal to their car brands. Finally it introduces a number of recommendations and set of directions for future research.

Key words: Automobile industry, Car brands, Brand loyalty, Brand preference, Brand awareness, Brand satisfaction, Brand repurchase.

Introduction

Companies which has a constant focus on customers are going to be the winner in the market. "A satisfied client will be a loyal customer". Marketing deals with identifying and meeting human and social desires. One of the shortest definitions of marketing is "meeting needs profitably". The aim of marketing is to know and understand that the products and services fits the customers and sells itself in the market. Marketing is designing the right product based on careful marketing research. The marketing concept in the mid 1950's have brought a lot of changes in the perception of the business concerns. Instead of product centered which believes

in 'make and sell' philosophy the business has shifted to customer centred i.e. 'sense and respond'. The job of the business is not to find the right customer for the product but the right product for the customer. In the 19th century the consumers would once place their trust in their friendly shopkeeper and in the bank themselves. In the 21st century the scenario is different. Now it is the brands themselves that are in trouble. They have become a victim of their own success. If a product fails, it the brand which is at fault.

Consumers don't blame the product, they blame the brand. The consumers has shifted their thinking from product blame to brand blame. Therefore their buying behaviour has changed. Brand loyalty is all about the attitude of the consumers towards a particular product. The American Marketing Association defines ' Brand loyalty' as, "The situation in which a consumer generally buys the same manufacture originated product or service repeatedly over time rather than buying from multiple suppliers within the category". Brand loyalty plays a major role in organisations success and future growth aspect. Satisfaction is the necessary condition to customer loyalty, even if the customers are satisfied with the brand they switch to other brands. Brand preference reflects a desire to use a particular company's products or services, even if there are multiple alternatives available. The contribution of India to the global sales of auto mobiles is set to grow. The automotive industry in India is one of the largest worldwide sector with more than 4 million cars produced in India. It is one of the Asia's largest markets. To add on Karnataka is the 4th largest contributor to the Indian automotive industry. As Bangalore is a silicon city which has a great number of vehicles and which is known for traffic we are concerned about the brand loyalty of customers on cars and the reasons why they choose one brand over the with special reference to the IT professionals.

Statement of the Problem

The emergence of more number of competing brands and unique models in the automobile industry has given rise to various questions that has to be answered. The question of whether electric cars will at some point replace petrol and diesel cars? Or is it due to the change in the standard of living, increase in the annual income, status, family size which will affect the brand loyalty of the customers? The rise in price of the cars due to the technology used, or modernising the car will affect brand loyalty. The quality of the product also influences the customer to shift his loyalty on brand. Due to the increase in the start-ups in Bangalore the population of the IT professionals are increasing at a higher rate. There is migration from different places across India as well as overseas. There is always a brand myth by the business

that “If a product is good, it will succeed”. This is untrue and is highly a debatable topic. If a product is not good enough to adapt to changing needs of the consumers they tend to fail in the market. IT professionals with their busy schedules prefer a good car which suits their financial budget, looks of the car and most preferably the style of the car. Usually the income level of the IT professionals are comparatively higher than the other income class of people. They tend to shift from one brand over the other as per their convenience.

Objectives

1. The main objective of this study is to discuss and analyze the brand loyalty of consumers towards the car brands. The research will also provide an insight of the study of brand preference and the reasons for shifting of one brand over the other.
2. This study contributes to the understanding of the buying behavior, attitude, brand satisfaction they have towards a particular car brand.

Research gap

This research intends to fill the research gap as there was less research done on automobile industry on examining the brand preference and brand loyalty targeting only the IT professional sector particularly in the Bangalore city.

Hypothesis development

H1: Customers don't prefer to buy the same brand they own at present and they are not loyal to the car brand.

H2: They prefer to buy a different model in the same brand they own at present and they are loyal to the car brand.

Review of Literature

1. Brown (1953) - His study highlighted the approach of classifying the degree of loyalty of the consumers where the consumers can be divided into four groups. The first group consists of “Hard Core loyals” who always prefers to buy the same brand. The second category of the consumers are called the “Split loyals”, who are loyal to two or more brands. The third group includes consumers who are loyal to one brand for a particular period of time but they tend to change from one brand to the other due to the advantages offered by the competitor's brand, these buyers are called as “Shifting

loyals". The last group is the "Switchers", these consumers shows no loyalty to any brand. They switch the brand according to their buying situation.

2. Assael (1974) -He examined the consumer involvement and identifies four brand loyalty driven types of consumers. Firstly the "Complex loyals" who will do research and then starts developing beliefs and attitudes about the brand and then they make a thoughtful choice. Secondly the "Dissonance loyals" are the ones who shop around and buy fairly quickly, as they may consider most brands in a given price range to be the same, even though expensive and self-expressive. In spite of experiencing dissonance noticing certain feature or hearing favorable things about other brands, they seek information to support their choice. Thirdly the "Habitual loyals", who make decisions based on brand familiarity and lastly the "Variety seekers" who shifts brands due to the variety rather than dissatisfaction, they choose brands with little evaluation and the evaluating process is done mostly during the consumption.
3. Aaker(1991)- He opined five levels of brand loyalty and splits customers accordingly into a "Loyalty pyramid" which resembles five types of consumers, firstly the "Non loyal consumers who do not have any particular interest towards the brands, secondly the "Satisfied consumers" who doesn't have any feeling of dissatisfaction of the brands, third is the satisfied consumers who incur switching costs, fourth is the consumers who truly like the brand and have an emotional attachment to it and lastly the "Committed consumers" who feel proud to have discovered and used the brand.
4. Dick and Basu (1994) - He argues that loyalty of the consumers are determined by the amount of strength of the relationship between relative brand attitude and repeat patronage related to it. A low relative attitude occurs during certain situations when a brand has low awareness like, after a recent introduction of the brand or when the brand is unable to communicate the well-defined advantages, where competing brands are seen as similar. On the basis of this attitude- behavior relationship, the author proposes four types of brand loyalty. Firstly a low relative attitude along with a high rate of repeat patronage is called "Spurious loyalty", secondly, where there is absence of loyalty implies to both low rate of repeat patronage and a low relative attitude. Thirdly when the relative brand attitude is high, the author identifies it as either "Latent loyalty" (low repeat patronage) or "Actual loyalty" and lastly when both relative attitude and repeat patronage have high levels, it is known as "True loyalty".
5. Bloemer and karper(1995)- Brand loyalty implies a deep commitment to brands and there is distinction between repeat purchases and actual brand loyalty, In their

published research, they convey that a repeat purchase behavior is the actual re-buying of a brand on the other hand loyalty includes a reason before the behavior. These authors further classify brand loyalty into “spurious and true loyalty”. Spurious loyalty represents biased behavioral response expressed overtime by some decision making unit, with respect to one or more alternate brands as a function of a tendency to do nothing or to remain unchanged. On the other hand True brand loyalty includes the above, but replaces inertia with brand awareness.

Scope of the study

The study has a scope of analysing the customer’s preference and loyalty on car brands. This empirical study is mostly benefitted to the automobile industry, manufacturing industry of cars, spare parts industry and will also facilitate researchers, scholars, teachers, academicians, professionals, practitioners, people who are interested in knowing about the brands which are existing in the market and to the vendors, dealers which will help them forecast the sales of cars and estimate the buying behaviour of customers towards cars and produce accordingly.

Significance of the study

The research work emphasis the significance of the study on brand loyalty and how important it is to study brand loyalty for the organizations which always thrives to survive in the market along with having their brand recognised in the market. In today’s fast-growing, instant gratification world, there are more choices than even before, companies are constantly coming up with new ways to try and get as many eyes on the product as possible. That’s why establishing a brand loyal consumer’s base is crucial in the existing market. If a company wants to establish a strong customer base it has to create brand loyalty. It doesn’t happen overnight. It requires engagement from the company to the consumer and production of quality products and services. For the organizations maintaining brand loyalty is of great importance.

Research Methodology

1. Types and sources of data- the study is based on the information collected from both primary and secondary data to study the buying behavior, degree of loyalty and brand preference of IT professionals. The respondents were asked to fill the questionnaires using an online survey (<https://docs.google.com/forms/u/o/>) google forms, open access journals and research papers.
2. Population and sample size- our study includes a sample size of 120 respondents namely IT professionals and only 94 respondents were considered for the study.
3. Sample procedure- the sampling technique used for the procurement of data is stratified sampling method.
4. Limitation of the study- the study is restricted to 120 respondents concentrating only on the IT professionals which is just an overview of few respondents which reflects the population of Bangalore.
5. Geographical area covered- the IT sector is one of the major contributors to boost the economy of India. Since Bangalore is known for its rich heritage of corporate sectors, the study focuses on Bangalore as the geographical area.
6. Reference period- the study is proposed to be limited to the analyses of brand loyalty of IT professionals on car brands in Bangalore city during the period of 3 months.

Data analysis and Interpretation

Table 1-Demographic profile of respondents

Educational qualification	Variables	Percentage
Diploma or below	6	6%
Graduate	73	73%
Post graduate	15	15%
Occupation		
Employee	80	80%
Self-employee	14	14%
Retired	0	0%
Marital status		
Unmarried	77	77%

Married	17	17%
Family income		
less than 7 lakhs p.a	66	66%
7- 15 lakhs p.a	25	25%
More than 15 lakhs p.a	3	3%

Source- Primary data

Interpretation- Demographic profile of the respondents as given in Table 1, majority of 73 respondents are graduates, 80 of them are employees and 66 of them are holding an annual income of less than 7 lakhs p.a.

Table 2- Factors which influenced or influences the respondents to purchase a car

Variables	No of respondents	Percentage
Family needs	52	55.3%
Increase in the family size	10	10.6%
Life style	22	23.4%
Other reasons	10	10.6%
TOTAL	94	94

Source- primary data

Interpretation- After the examination of the information collected regarding the factors influencing the respondents to purchase a car, it is evident that out of 94 IT professionals surveyed 52 respondents has availed the information about the factors which influenced or influence them as family needs, the second most factor which influenced the respondents is the life style which is preferred by 22 respondents and where 10 respondents chooses life style as their factor and the rest of the 10 respondents chooses other reasons.

Table 3- Factors which influences to prefer one car brand over the other

Variables	No of respondents	Percentage
Anti-lock braking system	1	1.1%
After sales services	5	5.3%
Mileage	33	35.1%
Exterior option	8	8.5%
Interior option	2	2.1%
Automatics	2	2.1%
Your budget	25	26.6%
Type of fuel consumption	2	2.1%
Storage and cargo capacity	1	1.063%
Looks or the style	15	16%
TOTAL	94	94

Source- primary data

Interpretation- An analysis of the factors which influences the buyer to prefer one car brand over the other signifies the importance of the variable i.e. “Mileage”. Maximum number i.e. 33 respondents out of 94 prefers “Mileage” as their factor. The next factor which influences them is the budget, where 25 out of 94 says that their budget plays a vital role. Similarly 15 respondents are influenced by the looks and style of the car brands. The rest of the respondents out of 94 prefer the other factors such as exterior option, after sales services, interior option and other factors which is preferred by least number of respondents.

Table 4- Different model in the same brand or shift to competitor's brand

Variable	No of respondents	Percentage
Definitely yes	76	80.9%
Definitely No	18	19.1%
TOTAL	94	94

Source- Primary data

Interpretation- The above result reveals that if one or more factors such as the after sales services, Mileage, exterior and interior options, automatics, budget, type of fuel consumption, storage and cargo capacity are found to be satisfactory, the respondents prefer to buy a different model in the same brand where 76 respondents out of 94 chooses the variable “Definitely yes” and 18 respondents out of 94 signifies that they will shift to the other competitors brand by choosing the variable “definitely No”.

Table 5- Satisfaction of the last purchased brand

Variables	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	72	76.6%
No	23	24.5%
Total	94	94

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: Majority of 72 respondents has indicated their view towards the satisfaction level of the last purchased brand by choosing ‘yes’ as their variable. This conveys that the respondents that was chosen for the study are satisfied of the brand which was previously

purchased. The remaining respondents doesn't seem to be satisfied by choosing 'No' as their variable. Since majority of people are satisfied, there is less chance of shifting to some other car brand.

Table 6- Intention of repurchasing the same brand next time

Variable	No of respondents	Percentage
Yes	44	46.8%
No	53	56.4%
Total	94	94

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: 53 out of 94 doesn't have an intention of repurchasing the same brand next time because of many factors which are influencing them such as the features or model offered by different competitors and 44 respondents chooses to repurchase the same brand next time. This signifies the brand satisfaction which they have towards the car brand.

Table 7- Recommending the last purchased brand to others

Variables	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	76	76
No	21	21
Total	94	94

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: 76 respondents out of 94 would like to recommend the brand that they have purchased to others and rest of the 21 respondents would not like to recommend the brand since they might have not been satisfied of the last purchased brand. Hence this survey reveals that majority of respondents are satisfied of the brand purchased and would like to recommend the same brand to others.

Table 8-Brand loyalty after price increase

Variable	No of respondents	Percentage
Yes	58	58%
No	37	37%
Total	94	94%

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: Majority of 58 respondents are ready to buy the same brand even if the brands price is increased in comparison to its competitor's brand and 37 of respondents doesn't seem to buy the same brand and they tend to shift to some other competitor brand

Findings

An analysis of the study reveals the following findings

- The study reveals that majority of the respondents are satisfied with the last purchased brand and there is less chance for them to shift from one car brand to the other. Since they are satisfied they recommend the last purchased brand to others.
- The respondents doesn't seem to have any intention of repurchasing the same brand next time as they look forward for special features like the looks, style, mileage , safety, which is much preferred when compared to the other factor.
- In a given situation of a particular brand price increase in comparison to the competitors price the respondents would still stay loyal to the existing car brand.

Suggestions

- The manufacturer of the car brand has to be veritable, genuine and harmonious to the customers, making sure that they are not ignored.
- Providing worth to the customers which they really care about is an important task which the car manufacturer has to explore by making an effort to know the factors which influences them to like or dislike a particular brand by understanding their personality.
- The automobile manufacturer of car brands must continue to enhance the reward loyalty programs for consumer in order to make sure that the consumer stay loyal to one particular car brand.
- The car producers must take adequate steps to take care of the customer's prime concern. They need to focus on the process of designing, sourcing of the products and product information.
- The manufacturer and to the lesser degree the retailer has greatest knowledge and expertise of the product or service when compared to the consumer. Hence the manufacturer are in a better position to consider risk than the consumer are, therefore they must take due care with respect to the production of cars with an inclusive of all feature such as safety, looks , mileage, accommodation, the executive and interior options and the other related features.
- For the producers to stay one step ahead of the competitors is a challenging endeavor. The buying pattern of the customers will be diverse. The producer, manufacturer, retailers have to think of being the only one of its kind in deciding the type of cars to be received by the consumers.

Conclusion

Based on the findings discussed above it can be observed that, no customers are loyal towards the brand until and unless the marketers treat the consumers as the “King of the market”. Marketing starts with consumer requirements and ends with consumer feedback. This research provides an overview of the brand loyalty of consumers where we have focused on the IT professionals of Bangalore city only. The primary purpose of this research was to determine the level of preference and loyalty of the consumers towards the car brands. Hypothesis two is accepted. Brand preference and brand satisfaction has a significant impact on the brand loyalty towards car brands. It means that an increase in the level of brand satisfaction and brand preference, it effects in the loyalty of brand. Brand satisfaction is strongly correlated with an intention to repurchase or to recommend the same car brand to others. It also influences the brand preferences of one car brand over the other. Majority of the consumers would like to buy the same car brand even if there is a price increase in comparison to the competitor’s brand. This reveals the degree of loyalty which they possess towards one particular car brand. Considering the strong relationship among the three dimensions we may conclude that brand satisfaction, brand preference and recommending the last purchased brand to others represent the ethos of brand loyalty.

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